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Review Article

**A REVIEW ON CURRENT TRENDS IN PHARMACEUTICAL
PACKAGING****Mr Kiran M. Kulkarni¹, Mr Saurabh Mane¹, Mr Manish S. Kondavar¹,
Mr. Shrikant magdum**¹Department of Pharmaceutical Chemistry, Appasaheb Birnale College of Pharmacy, Sangli,
Maharashtra, India, Kirankulkarni_1986@rediffmail.com**Article Received:** May 2020**Accepted:** June 2020**Published:** July 2020**Abstract:**

Packaging is an emerging science, an emerging engineering discipline, and a success contributor to pharmaceutical industries. The review details several of the recent pharmaceutical packaging trends that are impacting packaging industry, and offers some predictions for the future. Packaging is responsible for providing life-saving drugs, medical devices, medical treatments, and new products like medical nutritionals (nutraceuticals) in every imaginable dosage form to deliver every type of supplement, poultice, liquid, solid, powder, suspension, or drop to people the world over. It is transparent to the end user when done well and is open to criticism from all quarters when done poorly. Packaging can reside, or report through research and development (R and D), engineering, operations, purchasing, marketing, or the general administrative department of a company. For the majority of products produced in pharmaceutical industries it is probably the single largest aggregate purchase made by a company of materials critical to the protection, distribution, and sale of the product.

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INTRODUCTION: ^[1,2]

Packaging is defined as a technique which allows circumscription of pharmaceutical product from the time of production in a unit till its use. Role of pharmaceutical packaging is to provide lifesaving drugs, , nutraceuticals, powders, poultices, surgical devices, blood and blood products liquid and dosage forms, solid and semisolid dosage forms. Packaging of pharmaceuticals essentially provides circumscription, drug safety, identity, convenience of handling and delivery. Pharmaceutical packaging has to balance lots of complex contemplation. Classification of products is now more global than ever. Mass customisation of packaging to permit its use in multiple markets is a topic that needs exposition and discussion. Environmental affair, including sustainability, will always be a subjective significance to any packaging design. Pharmaceutical packaging firms are some of the industry's leading pioneer evident by the recent advancement in technology. Packaging is a science which is continuously evolving and is a major success patron for pharmaceutical industries. Packaging can reside, or report through research and development, pharmaceutical engineering, pharmaceutical operations, purchasing, marketing, or the general administrative department of a company. For the majority of products produced in pharmaceutical industries it is probably the single largest aggregate purchase made by a company of materials critical to the protection, distribution, and sale of the product.

Packaging is an evolving science, an emerging engineering discipline, and a success provider to pharmaceutical industries.

Leaving behind comparatively simple issues such as developing good designs and liaise with customers, pharmaceutical packagers are afraid to more pressing concerns which include fighting with copying, encouraging patient compliance, ensuring drug reliability and balancing child-resistance and availability for the elderly. Issue of environment safety is also key concern for both developed and developing countries packaging industry. Pharmaceutical packaging firms are some of the industry's leading innovators evident by the recent advancement in technology. The current trends are result of continuous series of challenges faced by industry.

New ideas of dynamic packaging, intelligent packaging and nanotechnology offers arrangements which play a vital part to improve or observing food quality and security and amplifying time span of usability.

1.ADVANTAGES OF PACKAGING.^[3]

- The integrity of dosage form is maintained.
- The side effects are minimized and the inert environment is maintained and protected from contamination.
- Packaging improves the shelf life of the product preventing deterioration of the product, thus enhancing better stability.
- Reduces the side effect
- It protects and withstand the quality of drug.
- It carries correct information and the identification code of the product.
- Protects against physical and biological damages.
- Protects against any damage caused by outer influences that can alter the property of the product.

2.OBJECTIVE OF PACKAGING ^[4]

- Provide satisfactory information regarding the contents.
- Package should have acceptable design and support patient compliance.
- **Physical protection.**
The drugs which are bounded in the package needs protection from shocks, high temperature, vibrations, compression which are generally caused by inadequate transportation and handling. So it is essential to have a package that can resist these problems & electrostatic discharge.
- **Barriers protection.**
A barrier from atmosphere is often required in order to prevent from environmental threats which may be caused by oxygen, water vapor, dust etc. Package permeability is crucial in design.
- **Information transmission.**
Labels and packages help to provide information related to the drugs and, dispose and recycle of the product. For pharmaceuticals, medicinal, chemicals and food products, some types of information are required by governments
- **Marketing-**
Packaging can be used by marcketers to encourage potential buyers to ourchase the product.
- **Convenience-**
Packaging can have features that ad convenience in distribution, handling, stacking, display, sale, opening, reclosing, use, dispensing & reuse.
- **Portion control-**

Packaging is useful to precise amount of contents to control usage.

Types Of Packaging^[5] :-

a) Primary packaging-

The material that first envelops the product and holds it. This is the smallest unit of distribution or use and is the package which is in direct contact with contents.

Example: ampules, IV containers

b) Secondary packaging-

It is outside the primary packaging used to group primary packages together.

Example: cartons box

c) Tertiary packaging –

It is used for bulk handling, warehouse storage and transport shipping.

Example: containers, barrel

1. TYPES OF PRIMARY AND SECONDARY PACKAGING MATERIAL^[6]

Table no 1- Types of packaging material

Sr.No.	Material	Type	USE
1.	GLASS	Type I-Borosilicate glass	Strong acids and Alkalis.
		Type II-Treated soda-lime glass	Neutral aqueous preparations & acidic preparations
		Type III- Regular soda lime glass	Dry Powders, Oleaginous solutions
		Type IV- General Purpose soda lime glass	For Suspension & Emulsion
2.	Plastic	Polyethylene(PE)	Food Packaging (Fruit juices, Milk)
		Polypropylene(PP)	Textiles, Living hinges
		Polyvinyl Chloride(PVC):	Blood bags, Plastic Wraps
		Polystyrene	Containers for Solid Dosage forms.
3.	Paper	-	Labels, patients information leaflet

2. Current trends in pharmaceutical packaging [6-11]

2.1 . Materials can be Coated Using Plasma Impulse Chemical Vapor Deposition

Although developed by Schott Glass, Plasma Impulse Chemical Vapor Deposition has been effective in coating high volume glass products, such as pharmaceutical vials, ampoules & syringes. Very rapidly it prospered in modifying the original PICVD process and applying bonded uniform coatings - in glass-like SiO₂ and TiO₂ oxide coatings to a wide range of plastics (e.g., PET,

PMMA, PC, COC, PP and HDPE). The result is that plastic can now have all the optimistic properties of glass. In the case of plastic lenses and display covers it is now possible to produce anti-scratch and antireflective coatings, while in the case of plastics packaging, a PICVD coating creates a obstruction against the passage of gas oxygen can no longer get in, and released carbon dioxide cannot get out. Accordingly, the contents have a longer shelf life with no effect on their taste.

Fig. no-1 Plasma Impulse Chemical Vapor Deposition

Fig. No.-2 Plasma Impulse Chemical Vapor Deposition Process

5.2. Child-Resistant Packaging-

Child-resistant packaging (CRP) or C-R packaging is special packaging used to decrease the hazard of children ingesting dangerous items. The CRP containers resist penetration by children but can be opened by adults. This is often accomplished by the use of a special safety cap with locking mechanism.

It is mandatory by rule for prescription drugs, over-the-counter medications, pesticides, insecticides and household chemicals. In some jurisdictions, unit packaging such as blister packs is also structured for child safety.

It has been made necessary to pack drugs like, Elemental iron, Aspirin, Paracetamol Contraceptives and many other drugs to be packed in CRP.

Fig. No- 4 Child-resistant packaging

Fig. No-5 Ziplock bags

5.3. Ziplock bags-

Recent popular advancements in packaging design include ziplock bags, providing a lightweight and compact way of securing both traditional and cannabis-based medicine. Ziplock packaging is a single-entry design that requires mature dexterity to slide a zipper open to access the contents. Many designs even include a flap that covers the zipper when the bag is closed, disguising the entry point as an added layer of security.

Packaging manufacturers also have a duty to label child-resistant packaging clearly for consumers. This includes using complete terms like ‘child-resistant packaging’ rather than abbreviations and including the information in a specified place – the ‘how supplied/storage and handling section’ of the label. Separate adhesive labels are seen as best practice compared with on-packaging.

5.4. Eco-friendly Packaging

5.4.1. Green packaging

“By using biomaterials our consumers contribute to the decrease of greenhouse gas emissions, thereby defending the environment and avoiding needless waste. Biomaterials are the renewable substitute to predictable PE/PET.”

Sugarcane is one of the materials used to make biomaterials. It produces a material with precisely the same features as conventional plastics which is also fully recyclable.

Fig. No -6 Green Packaging

5.4.2. Paper and board

The main benefits of paper and board are their low cost for a given level of rigidity, and their superb printability and promotional potential. They also have a good environmental image because they are characteristically biodegradable and their raw materials are renewable.

Paperboard materials are admirably suited for highly decorated and promotional packages, widely used to give an excellent-quality image. Paper and paperboard are both made from cellulose fibres, obtained mainly from wood. Raw material sources for paper and paperboard contain logs, and by-products of the timber industry such as sawdust, as well as recycled fibre from newsprint, magazines, books and other paperboard sources.

Fig. No – 7 Paperboard materials For Packaging

However, paper and board have no barrier to gases and lose their strength and rigidity when wet. They therefore have to be coated and/or coated with impermeable materials to obtain these properties. As a result, it is technically challenging and expensive, though not impossible, to re-pulp and recycle these materials for use in comparable applications.

To overcome this deficiency, the packaging industry has developed ways of reusing the waste from, for example, laminated beverage packaging made from board, aluminium and polyethylene.

Moreover, paper and paperboard products cannot be recycled indefinitely since the fibres tend to deteriorate and shorten in length progressively with each cycle. In addition, adhesives and tapes used in conjunction with these materials can clog the recycling equipment.

5.4.3. Glass

Producing glass from its raw materials, sand and soda ash, requires high initial energy inputs. Use of recycled glass in the creation of new bottles and jars needs substantially less energy and is thus superior from the supply conservation standpoint. Its main disadvantages are its weight and fragility, and its weakness to abrupt temperature instabilities.

Glass Bottles Used For Pharmaceutical Packaging

5.4.4. Steel

Steel has predictably been recycled worldwide, since as much as 40% of steel scrap goes into the creation of new steel. Every can produced contains, on average, 25% recycled steel.

Its main advantage over other packaging materials from an environmental angle is that it can be readily and cheaply separated from mixed waste using magnets. As much as 50% reduction in energy use can be realized by mixing a fraction of scrap with the virgin steel. Tinplate scrap can be recycled at levels of up to 100% for applications other than packaging.

The main drawback of steel is that, like glass, it is a heavy material with low intrinsic value. In addition, only a small percentage of steel and tinplate-can scrap lends itself to recycling into steel for can-making. Steel-can recycling is thus less economically viable than, for example, recycling of aluminium.

Fig. No - 7 Steel Cans Used In Pharmaceutical Packaging

5.4.5. Aluminium

Aluminium is an ideal material for recycling. It has high intrinsic worth, and hence scrap value. There is thus a substantial incentive to regain the metal from packaging waste. The economics of collection and recycling of aluminium for packaging applications are generally favourable.

The fact that recycling does not destroy aluminium means that new aluminium can be made from

100%-recycled material. This has enabled the creation of a practically closed-loop system, the only packaging material for which such a facility is available.

Fig. No – 8 Aluminum Tubes Used For Packaging Of Creams

5.4.6. Wood

Wood is relatively heavy and can be expensive as packaging. It provides no effective barrier to gases or moisture and its use in food packaging is therefore restricted. As a result, the use of wood in packaging, although still widespread, is in decline.

5.4.7. Jute and bamboo

Jute and bamboo are no longer generally observed as suitable packaging materials for exporting foodstuffs, because of the contamination possibilities that their open package configurations such as sacks and baskets can present.

Fig. No – 8 Jute Bags Used For Packaging

3. Talk-in packaging^[12-14]

1.The talk Pack from wipak walsrode GmbH in Germany a system which can be invisibly integrated into any printed image on any packaging material, but need a special scanning pen.

2.A recent development by VTT technical research central of Finland using tags with NFC (Near Field Communication) based technology connected to NFC-enabled mobile phones to download text, audio or web page product information, which can be played back on their handset.

6.1. TalkPack –wipac

A special pen –shaped reader is used to retrieve the stored information and to replay it as audio files and render speech, music or sound an audible and thus the consumer can obtain information on the manufacturer, brand, shelf-life or other information.

Tack pack does not require any RFID or microchips.

The dot code is simply printed on top of images and texts using a special varnish. This technology can be used with all printing technologies.

Fig No- 8 Talk Pack –wipe pen –shaped reader

6.2. NFC Tags-

NFC tags are added to any packaging so a consumer could touch the code on the packaging with their NFC-enabled mobile phone to download text, audio or information, which can be played back on his phone. Delivered vocal dosage instructions from pharmacy staff, to aid a visually impaired or blind person.

Fig. No- 9 NFC-enabled mobile phone

Fig. No- 10 NFS TAG

4. Dispensing caps [15-17]

Dispensing caps or functional caps – store dry or liquid supplements separately from the water- released by the consumer they form an energy or vit. Drinks or medicinal drinks. Everything from pharmaceuticals to nutraceuticals, from antiaging to anti-oxidants, from vit. to functional supplements, from male potency to functional supplements, from male every to relaxation and so on can be packed and properly dosed by a dispensed cap.

It is generally claimed that pills and capsules have a very short window of absorption

Liquid absorption is much higher –around 80-90%

Fig. No- 11 Different Types Of Dispensing Caps

Fig. No- 12 Mechanism Of Dispensing Caps

CONCLUSION:

As the packaging of the pharmaceutical products is very important with regard to its stability, acceptance to patient, transport, etc. There is always

scope for advancement and improvement of the pharmaceutical packaging. Therefore, new techniques like Child-Resistant Packaging, Talk-in packaging, Eco-friendly Packaging, Dispensing caps etc. seems to be promising in pharmaceutical products packaging.

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